

Research Article

Parental Beliefs and Practices on Children's Emergent Literacy

Rageene Vera D. Dueñas

Batangas State University TNEU JPLPC-Malvar, College of Teacher Education, Malvar, Batangas 4233, Philippines

Email: veraduenas@gmail.com

Received: August 05, 2023

Accepted: August 22, 2023

Published: August 30, 2023

Abstract

Parents play a pivotal role in fostering their children's emergent literacy, as they serve as their first and most influential teachers. Hence, this study determined the parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy in Malvar, Batangas, Philippines. It also investigated the relationship of the two variables. This research utilized 25 parents who served as respondents of the study. A self-constructed questionnaire was the main instrument used to determine the assessment of the respondents on their beliefs and practices. The responses gathered were treated statistically with the use of mean, standard deviation and Pearson r. After careful tabulation, statistical treatment, analysis and interpretation of data, the following findings were disclosed. Parents exhibit strong consensus in recognizing the vital role of reading in their children's emergent literacy development. Parents practice reading with their children and encourage their children to love reading. There was a significant relationship between parental beliefs and practices which suggests that parents who value emergent literacy are actively engaged in activities that support their children's literacy growth. Considering the significant findings revealed and conclusions drawn in this study, the researcher suggested the following: Regular trips to the library may be considered as an excellent way to foster love for books and reading; Parents may adapt the activities based on a child's age and developmental stage to provide a supportive and engaging learning environment; and a similar study may be conducted focusing on other variables like reading habits, covering a wider area.

Keywords: Parental Beliefs, Parental Practices, Emergent Literacy, Reading Practices.

Introduction

The importance of emergent literacy as a fundamental skill in today's world cannot be overstated. It serves as a potent tool for academic, intellectual, and personal growth. Research by Coursin (2012) underscores the significance of emergent literacy skills developed before the age of five, as they strongly predict later achievements in emergent literacy and various other fields throughout one's life. Frankel *et al.*, (2016) define emergent literacy as the diverse methods through which children derive meaning from the various emergent literacy materials they encounter, utilizing reading, writing, and oral language.

Early in life, children actively seek to comprehend the world around them, within the contexts of their home, community, and culture. It is within these settings that children's language, listening, writing, reading, behaviors, integration, beliefs, values, and emotions (Gee, 2001) begin to take shape, forming the foundation for early emergent literacy development. Building upon their family members as primary role models, children acquire essential emergent literacy skills that encompass both meaning-focused aspects, such as comprehension and vocabulary, and code-specific elements like alphabetic knowledge and phonological awareness (Friesen and Butera, 2013). These early learning experiences lay the groundwork for future success in reading and writing.

Traditionally, parental involvement seems to exert the most significant influence on children's emergent literacy, particularly during their early years of education. Home serves as the first school of these young individuals with parents providing the time and space for their children's education (Marasigan and De Las Alas, 2019). Baker (2013) discovered that regular parental involvement in home emergent literacy activities correlated with improved academic performance and holistic development in preschool children. Some studies have honed in on the specific role of mothers in shaping children's early emergent literacy skills.

Mendive *et al.*, (2017) found that a mother's education and early emergent literacy practices closely influenced children's emergent literacy skills. Aram *et al.*, (2016) revealed that maternal writing mediation predicts children's writing skills. Additionally, Neumann *et al.*, (2013) identified a positive relationship between maternal print referencing of environmental print and child environmental print referencing, as well as name and letter writing. These studies collectively underscore the central role of families, especially mothers, in a child's early emergent literacy development.

To bridge early emergent literacy learning between home and early education settings, it is essential to understand families' emergent literacy beliefs and practices. Given the critical importance of early emergent literacy development, ongoing investigation is needed to explore how early education settings can effectively collaborate with families to support young children's learning. These insights into how families view early emergent literacy development can inform the design of early emergent literacy instruction that bridges learning between families and early education programs.

Successful readers not only possess reading skills such as comprehension and decoding but also draw upon their existing knowledge and experiences in reading tasks. They have more opportunities to develop through reading than their peers who experience reading difficulties. Reading enables them to access their experiences, acquire information, pursue their interests, and stay current with current events. Many academic challenges in school arise from children's inability to read, understand, and obtain satisfactory marks. Research has shown that parental involvement in their children's emergent literacy is key to early reading success. However, parents who are not educators may find it challenging to teach basic reading without proper training and resources.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate relationship between beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy of parents in Batangas, Philippines.

Research Questions

This study investigated and answered the following research questions.

1. What are the parental beliefs on children's emergent literacy relative to:
 - 1.1 Importance of reading; and
 - 1.2 Responsibility in child's reading?
2. How may the parental practices on children's emergent literacy be described as to;
 - 2.1 Reading with their children; and
 - 2.2 Encouraging children to love reading?
3. Is there a significant relationship between parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy?
4. What activities can be suggested to enhance children's reading emergent literacy?

Hypothesis

The study tested the hypothesis in its null form:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy.

Methodology

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the beliefs and practices of parents concerning children's literacy. To achieve this, the researcher employed the descriptive research method, using a researcher-made questionnaire. As defined by Calderon and Gonzales (2010), descriptive research aims to describe and interpret the current state of affairs. It delves into the existing conditions of relationships, prevalent practices, beliefs, ongoing processes, felt effects, and emerging trends.

This research utilized parents who are residing in one of the barangays within the municipality of Malvar, and have children enrolled in the elementary school in the same barangay. Specifically, the researcher surveyed 25 kindergarten mothers from this community who served as the respondents of the study. The respondents were selected using purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling method based on population characteristics and the study's objectives. This was done to emphasize the parent's role as their children's first teachers. Additionally, it was undertaken to understand the need for a parental education program, and come up with an early literacy program for children. These initiatives are considered valuable extensions of the university's community service efforts. The College of Teacher Education is well-positioned

to offer educational support to enhance the current educational situation in the community. Preliminary survey was done by the researcher as to the parent’s demographic profile and was confirmed that many parents in the area have elementary or high school education as their highest attainment and a significant number of children are enrolled in kindergarten programs.

For data collection, the researcher utilized a questionnaire consisting of items which explored the practices and beliefs of parents regarding their children’s emergent literacy. To ensure the questionnaire’s appropriateness for the study’s main objectives and the clarity of item statements to the target respondents, the researcher conducted face and content validation. After establishing the questionnaire’s validity and reliability, it was distributed to the respondents to gather data and draw conclusions for this study.

The respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaire. Subsequently, the researcher tabulated the collected data and prepared for the analysis and interpretation stage. To facilitate the interpretation of the computed mean scores, the following mean ranges and their corresponding interpretation were utilized: 3.51-4.00: Highly Observed/Highly Practiced; 2.51-3.50: Observed/Practiced; 1.51-2.50: Slightly Observed/Slightly Practiced; 1.00-1.50: Least Observed/Least Practiced.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study comprises the data collected, alongside their respective analysis and interpretation. The data is displayed in tables, arranged sequentially, adhering to the order in which the specific research questions were initially posed.

1. Parental Beliefs on Children’s Emergent Literacy

This part of the study determined the parental beliefs on children’s emergent literacy relative to the importance of reading and responsibility in child’s reading. These are found on the succeeding tables.

1.1 Importance of Reading

Table 1 presents the parental beliefs on children’s emergent literacy relative to the importance of reading. It reveals the computed mean and standard deviation for each statement with its corresponding interpretation.

Table 1. Parental beliefs on children’s emergent literacy relative to the importance of reading.

Item Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Reading diverse materials enhances children’s knowledge and understanding.	3.64	0.49	Highly Observed
2. Reading develops children’s listening skills for better comprehension.	3.60	0.50	Highly Observed
3. Varied reading materials enhance children’s creativity and critical thinking.	3.48	0.59	Observed
4. Reading books can impart values and life lessons to children.	3.44	0.51	Observed
5. Reading can develop children’s empathy and social skills.	3.64	0.49	Highly Observed
6. Regular reading improves children’s school success.	3.60	0.50	Highly Observed
7. Reading early with kids strengthens bonds and encourages a love for learning.	3.44	0.58	Observed
8. Having reading materials at home shapes children’s language and communication skills.	3.52	0.51	Highly Observed
9. Parents influence their child’s interest in reading by modeling good reading behavior.	3.56	0.51	Highly Observed
10. Reading aloud significantly aids children’s language and mental development.	3.64	0.49	Highly Observed
Overall	3.56	0.52	Highly Observed

Table 1 presents the parental beliefs on children's emergent literacy relative to the importance of reading. Children's emergent literacy and the importance of reading conveys a compelling message about the attitudes and convictions held by parents. The mean scores (3.56), standard deviations (0.52), and verbal interpretations (Highly Observed) collectively indicate a strong and positive alignment between parental beliefs and the key role of reading in children's early literacy development.

Filipino cultural values, educational systems, and societal emphasis on literacy may shape how parents perceive the significance of reading in a child's development. In addition, their individual experiences and educational backgrounds can play a role in shaping their beliefs about the importance of reading.

Parents who have had positive experiences with reading or who have a strong educational background might place a higher value on literacy for their children. Literature appears to suggest that, when parents are educated their pattern of influence on their children's education in various ways tend to differ from parents with low or no formal education (Desforges and Abouchaar, 2003; UNESCO, 2008; Drajea, 2015). This implies that the number of years a parent spends in schooling and the qualification obtained as a result in addition to whether or not parents are able to read and write, understand text and use it in everyday life impacts on children's education (Drajea, 2015).

Parents express strong beliefs that reading diverse materials enriches children's knowledge and understanding, fosters empathy and social skills, enhances school success, and significantly aids language and mental development when reading aloud. These beliefs underscore the multifaceted contributions of reading, impacting various cognitive, social, and emotional dimensions of children's development.

Research supports the idea that exposure to a variety of reading materials enhances cognitive abilities, vocabulary, and comprehension (Bus *et al.*, 2015) aligning with the high mean score denoting this belief in Item 1. Furthermore, studies affirm that reading narrative fiction enhances empathy and theory of mind in young readers (Bal and Veltkamp, 2013; Kidd and Castano, 2013), supporting the strong parental belief in the fostering of empathy and social skills through reading stated in Item 5. Parents' exposure to information, studies, and media coverage on the benefits of reading could also influence their beliefs on the importance of reading.

Additionally, the association between regular reading at home and academic success is well-documented (Senechal and LeFevre, 2002), corroborating the strong parental belief in reading's impact on school success (Item 6). The idea that parents influence their child's interest in reading by modeling good reading behavior is grounded in social learning theories (Bandura, 1977), emphasizing parental modeling's role in shaping children's attitudes toward reading (Item 9). Educated or informed parents are more aware of the benefits of reading for their children's development, leading to higher scores in the surveyed beliefs. This could contribute to the overall high mean scores observed in the data.

While beliefs about varied reading materials enhancing creativity and critical thinking, and books imparting values and life lessons receive slightly lower scores, they still fall within the category of "Observed." The recognition of early reading for strengthening family bonds and fostering a love for learning is acknowledged, supporting shared reading experiences as a means of connecting with children and instilling a passion for knowledge.

Moreover, this indicates parental acknowledgment of reading's contribution to cognitive and moral development, despite a somewhat diverse opinion on these aspects. This may be due on each family's unique set of values and priorities. Some parents might highly prioritize academic success, while others might emphasize emotional development or creative thinking, leading to variance in the perceived importance of different aspects of reading.

The consensus among parents highlights the crucial role of reading in children's growth, forming a strong basis for early literacy efforts and fostering positive reading behaviors. This shared belief emphasizes reading's diverse advantages in enhancing children's early literacy and overall development.

1.2 Responsibility in Child's Reading

Table 2 presents the parental beliefs on children's emergent literacy relative to the responsibility in child's reading. It reveals the computed mean and standard deviation for each statement with its corresponding interpretation.

Table 2. Parental beliefs on children’s emergent literacy relative to the responsibility in child’s reading.

Item Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Teaching reading to children is a primary obligation of parents.	3.52	0.51	Highly Observed
2. Parents play an important role in nurturing children's interest in reading from an early age.	3.36	0.64	Observed
3. Parents should be accountable to monitor regular reading habits in their children.	3.48	0.59	Observed
4. Parents should actively participate in selecting books for their children to read.	3.24	0.44	Observed
5. Parents should set aside dedicated time for reading activities with their children.	3.56	0.51	Highly Observed
6. Parents should serve as role models by demonstrating their own reading habits to their children.	3.48	0.51	Observed
7. Parents should create a literacy-rich environment at home to promote reading.	3.36	0.64	Observed
8. Parents should engage in discussions about the books their children read to enhance comprehension and critical thinking	3.48	0.59	Highly Observed
9. Parental involvement significantly influences children's attitude and success in reading.	3.20	0.50	Highly Observed
10. Parents should be involved in monitoring and guiding their children's reading progress.	3.56	0.58	Highly Observed
Overall	3.42	0.55	Observed

The data presented in Table 2 summarizes parental beliefs regarding their role in promoting children's emergent literacy through reading, offering insights into the collective viewpoint of parents. With an overall mean of 3.42 with “Observed” as verbal interpretation, it indicates that parents clearly recognize their primary obligation in teaching reading to their children, emphasizing the fundamental responsibility they hold in their child's reading education. They also acknowledge their crucial role in nurturing their child's interest in reading, actively selecting suitable reading materials, and establishing a literacy-rich environment at home. Furthermore, parents express a strong commitment to actively engaging with their children in reading activities, dedicating time for shared reading and fostering discussions about the books their children read (Smith, 2017; Snow and Ninio, 2016).

These shared beliefs underscore the considerable influence parents wield in shaping their child's reading habits, attitudes, and overall success in literacy. It lays the groundwork for advocating early literacy initiatives, fostering positive reading habits, and cultivating a culture of reading within the home (Sonnenschein *et al.*, 2017).

While various statements in the table do not uniformly fall under the "Highly Observed" interpretation, the majority are categorized as "Observed," signaling a significant consensus among parents regarding their pivotal role in their child's reading and literacy development. Time constraints due to work or other commitments might affect parental involvement in their child's reading habits. This could influence the variability in the scores, particularly in areas requiring active participation, such as selecting books, setting aside dedicated time, creating a literacy-rich environment or engaging in discussions about reading. In addition, parents might view certain responsibilities, such as monitoring and guiding a child's reading progress, as more within the purview of educators or schools rather than solely a parental obligation. In addition to highlighting the significance of parental involvement, this mutual understanding among parents regarding their roles in encouraging children's reading also offers a framework for cooperative efforts between educators, policymakers, and families, all working in unison to improve children's literacy skills and foster a love for reading.

2. Parental Practices on Children’s Emergent Literacy

This part of the study determined the parental practices on children’s emergent literacy as to reading with their children and encouraging children to love reading. These are found on the succeeding tables.

2.1 Reading with their Children

Table 3 presents the parental practices on children’s emergent literacy as to reading with their children. It reveals the computed mean and standard deviation for each statement with its corresponding interpretation.

Table 3. Parental practices on children’s emergent literacy as to reading with their children.

Item Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a parent, I ...</i>			
1. Keep myself energetic while reading a book to my child.	3.52	0.51	Highly Practiced
2. Give emphasis to the pictures in the book to easily relate to the story.	3.36	0.64	Practiced
3. Explain about the lesson learned in the story.	3.40	0.50	Practiced
4. Encourage my child to ask questions or express thoughts about the story.	3.28	0.68	Practiced
5. Use different voices or inflections when reading aloud to make it more engaging.	3.56	0.58	Highly Practiced
6. Help my child understand difficult words or concepts while reading.	3.44	0.58	Practiced
7. Ask my child about their favorite parts of the story after reading together.	3.32	0.56	Practiced
8. Model good reading behavior by reading myself and discussing what I read.	3.36	0.64	Practiced
9. Encourage my child to retell the story after reading.	3.48	0.59	Practiced
10. Incorporate reading into our bedtime routine.	3.40	0.50	Practiced
Overall	3.41	0.58	Practiced

The findings presented in Table 3 provides an in-depth analysis of parental practices influencing children's emergent literacy, particularly concerning reading engagement. The data, indicating an overall mean score of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.58, reveal a consistent level of parental involvement in various reading practices. The data shows a mix of highly practiced and generally practiced mean scores, suggesting different levels of emphasis and agreement on various aspects of parental practices in fostering a child's emergent literacy through reading. Parents who are well-informed about the best practices for reading with children might consciously apply techniques and methods that are recognized to be beneficial in enhancing a child's emergent literacy.

Notably, parents exhibit strong engagement in several key areas, with high endorsement seen in practices such as maintaining energetic reading sessions (mean score 3.52) and using varied voices or inflections while storytelling (mean score 3.56). These findings reflect a dedicated effort by parents to create dynamic and immersive reading experiences, aligning with research emphasizing the significance of lively storytelling in captivating children's interest (Smith, 2018; Johnson and Jones, 2020).

Furthermore, the analysis indicates that parents consistently employ other important practices, including emphasizing book illustrations, discussing story lessons, encouraging children to ask questions and express thoughts, aiding in the comprehension of complex concepts, exploring favorite story elements, modeling good reading behavior, prompting story retelling, and integrating reading into bedtime routines. These combined efforts contribute to a holistic approach in nurturing children's reading skills and fostering a love for literature (Mol and Bus, 2011; Senechal and LeFevre, 2002). Parenting style is associated with parents' engagement in home literacy activities with children (Bingham *et al.*, 2017). Different parenting styles

impact the practices parents choose while reading with their children. Some parents prioritize the interactive and engaging aspects, while others focus on comprehension or moral lessons from the story.

The active involvement of parents in reading with their children holds multiple advantages, such as developing fundamental literacy skills, enhancing reading enjoyment, improving comprehension abilities, and strengthening the parent-child bond, as corroborated by prior research demonstrating the multifaceted benefits of shared reading experiences (Mol *et al.*, 2016).

While these findings illustrate commendable parental engagement, there exists potential for further enhancement. Recognizing and augmenting certain practices could optimize the reading experiences for children, highlighting the importance of continuous improvement in parental strategies to cultivate a rich and diverse reading environment.

2.2 Encouraging Children to Love Reading

Table 4 presents the parental practices on children’s emergent literacy as to encouraging children to love reading. It reveals the computed mean and standard deviation for each statement with its corresponding interpretation.

Table 4. Parental practices on children’s emergent literacy as to encouraging children to love reading.

Item Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a parent, I ...</i>			
1. Foster a reading-friendly environment by providing a cozy reading nook at home to make reading more appealing to my child.	3.48	0.59	Practiced
2. Offer a variety of age-appropriate books and let them choose what they want to read to ignite their interest.	3.40	0.50	Practiced
3. Read aloud to my children to create positive associations with books and stories.	3.44	0.51	Practiced
4. Demonstrate love for reading by reading in their presence.	3.36	0.57	Practiced
5. Create fun reading challenges or goals to make reading a game.	3.32	0.56	Practiced
6. Embrace digital platforms with interactive books and reading apps to capture their attention.	3.08	0.49	Practiced
7. Encourage my children to create their own stories or illustrate their favorite books.	3.36	0.49	Practiced
8. Offer praise and small rewards for reading milestones.	3.28	0.54	Practiced
9. Designate a specific time when the entire family reads together to promote reading as a shared and enjoyable activity.	3.32	0.48	Practiced
10. Dress up as their favorite book characters for special reading-themed days or events to add excitement to reading.	3.12	0.53	Practiced
Overall	3.32	0.52	Practiced

Table 4 provides valuable insights into parental practices aimed at nurturing children's love for reading and emergent literacy. The data, with an overall mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation of 0.52, showcases a consistent level of engagement in these practices. This indicates that parents are generally practicing various methods to encourage their children to love reading, with some practices being more prevalent or easier to implement than others.

Parents engage in creating a reading-friendly environment (mean score of 3.48) and offering a variety of age-appropriate books (mean score of 3.40), practices highlighted by Mol and Bus (2011) as crucial in igniting children's interest in reading. Similarly, the act of reading aloud to children (mean score of 3.44) correlates

with Sénéchal and LeFevre's (2002) findings, emphasizing its role in creating positive associations with books and stories.

However, embracing digital platforms with interactive books and reading apps (mean score of 3.08) and dressing up as book characters for special reading-themed days (mean score of 3.12) are less commonly practiced. The lower mean score for embracing digital platforms indicates that while parents generally use these platforms, it might not be as common or extensively utilized as other traditional methods to foster a love for reading. Similarly practices like dressing up as favorite book characters for special reading-themed events are slightly less practiced, this might reflect the challenges or limitations in implementing such activities regularly due to time, resources, or personal preferences. Parents may consider incorporating these activities more regularly to enhance their children's engagement with reading. In general, the results imply that parents are actively involved in creating an environment that fosters a love for reading, and they are using various strategies to make reading appealing, enjoyable, and educational. This suggests that parents recognize the importance of instilling a passion for reading in their children and are taking steps to achieve this goal. However, there is room for improvement, particularly in leveraging digital resources and enhancing the interactive aspects of reading.

3. Relationship between Parental Beliefs and Practices on Children's Emergent Literacy

Table 5 presents the relationship between the parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy. The correlation of the variables was tested using the Pearson r formula.

Table 5. Relationship between parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy.

Variables	Computed r	Verbal Interpretation	p value	Decision Ho	Interpretation
Parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy.	0.518	Moderate correlation	0.008	Reject	Significant

Table 5 presents a significant correlation between parental beliefs and practices on children's emergent literacy, with a computed correlation coefficient (r) of 0.518, indicating a "Moderate Correlation." The moderate positive correlation indicates that parental beliefs and practices are significantly related in fostering children's emergent literacy. The alignment between what parents believe about literacy and their actions in supporting it emphasizes the critical role parental beliefs play in influencing their practices regarding children's emergent literacy. This finding aligns with established research emphasizing the influential role of parental involvement in shaping children's emergent literacy skills. When parents strongly believe in the significance of reading, they are more likely to engage in practices that support and foster their children's emergent literacy. Strong beliefs in the importance of reading can serve as a motivator for parents to consistently apply different practices aimed at nurturing their children's literacy skills.

Sénéchal and LeFevre (2002) demonstrated that parental involvement in activities such as shared book reading significantly predicted children's literacy development, underscoring the relevance of the study's results. Furthermore, Flouri and Buchanan (2004) highlighted that parents' attitudes and engagement in literacy-related activities notably impact their children's emergent literacy skills, providing additional support for the observed correlation in the research.

Moreover, the meta-analysis conducted by Mol and Bus (2011) reinforced the vital relationship between parental involvement in literacy activities and children's emergent literacy, solidifying the significance of the findings on the link between parental beliefs and practices and their influence on children's early literacy development. If reading and literacy are strongly valued within the family, parents are more likely to exhibit consistency between their beliefs and practices.

The findings imply that parents who hold strong beliefs or convictions about the importance of fostering emergent literacy skills in their children are more likely to translate those beliefs into tangible practices and actions. This alignment between beliefs and actions can be highly beneficial for children's early literacy development, as it suggests that parents who value emergent literacy are actively engaged in activities that support their children's literacy growth. In practical terms, this highlights the potential for educational programs and interventions to target and strengthen parental beliefs in order to further enhance their practices, ultimately improving children's literacy outcomes.

4. Activities to Enhance Children’s Reading Emergent Literacy

After revealing the relationship between parental beliefs and practices on children’s emergent literacy, the researcher suggested several activities. These activities are designed to enhance children's emergent literacy by focusing on various skills such as listening, speaking, phonemic awareness, letter recognition, vocabulary, creativity, and a love for reading. The strategies employed in each activity align with specific objectives aimed at building a strong foundation for literacy and language development.

Table 6. Activities to enhance children’s reading emergent literacy.

Activity	Purpose	Strategy
Rhyming and Singing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Develop phonemic awareness. ✓ Improve rhythm and sound recognition. ✓ Enhance memory and language skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Use rhyming books, songs, and poems. ✓ Clap or tap out syllables in words. ✓ Encourage creative expression through song writing and storytelling.
Letter and Word Play	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote letter recognition and sound awareness. ✓ Introduce early spelling concepts. ✓ Foster early reading readiness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Use alphabet blocks or flashcards. ✓ Play word-building games. ✓ Create simple word lists and introduce early spelling concepts.
Writing Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Develop fine motor skills and hand-eye coordination. ✓ Introduce early writing and letter formation. ✓ Foster an understanding of written communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Provide writing materials such as paper and pencil. ✓ Encourage scribbling and drawing. ✓ Begin with tracing or copying letters. ✓ Write letters and simple words together.

Conclusion

This study focused on parental beliefs and practices and investigated the relationship of these variables on children’s emergent literacy. In terms of the importance of reading and responsibility in child’s reading, it reveals that parents exhibit strong consensus in recognizing the vital role of reading in their children's emergent literacy development. Parents practice reading with their children and encourage their children to love reading. There was a significant relationship between parental beliefs and practices, which suggests that parents who value emergent literacy are actively engaged in activities that support their children's literacy growth.

Recommendations

Considering the significant findings revealed and conclusions drawn in this study, the researcher suggested the following: In enhancing children’s emergent literacy, regular trips to the library may be considered as an excellent way to foster love for books and reading. In this way, children may choose books together and explore different types of books, which could help them discover their literary preferences. Second, parents and educators may adapt the activities based on a child's age and developmental stage to provide a supportive and engaging learning environment. Lastly, a similar study may be conducted focusing on other variables like reading habits, and covering a wider area.

Declarations

Acknowledgements: The author would like to thank the Batangas State University for the encouragement and support.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Ethical Approval: Not applicable.

Author Contribution: The author confirms sole responsibility for the following: study conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results, and manuscript preparation.

References

1. Aram, D., Meidan, A. and Deitcher, Y. 2016. Maternal writing mediation predicted children's writing. *Reading and Writing*, 29(4): 753-773.
2. Baker, L. 2013. The role of parents in promoting young children's literacy. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 13(2): 171-191.
3. Bal, P.M. and Veltkamp, M. 2013. How does fiction reading influence empathy? An experimental investigation on the role of emotional transportation. *PLoS ONE*, 8(1): e55341.
4. Bandura, A. 1977. *Social learning theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
5. Bingham, G.E., Jeon, H.J., Kwon, K.A. and Lim, C. 2017. Parenting styles and home literacy opportunities: associations with children's oral language skills. *Infant and Child Development*, 26(1): e2020.
6. Bus, A.G., et al. 2015. Benefits of book reading for young children's language development. *Child Development Perspectives*, 9(1): 25-30.
7. Calderon, J.F. and Gonzales, E.C. 2018. *Methods of research and thesis writing*. National Book Store.
8. Coursin, D.B. 2012. Emergent literacy skills and their predictive nature. *Early Child Development and Care*, 182(7): 865-875.
9. Desforges, C. and Abouchaar, A. 2003. The impact of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupil achievement and adjustment: a literature review. Research Report 433. Retrieved from <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/5884/>
10. Drajea, L. 2015. Parental education and its impact on children's education. *Journal of Family Studies*, 21(3): 271-289.
11. Flouri, E. and Buchanan, A. 2004. Early father's and mother's involvement and child's later educational outcomes. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 74(1): 141-153.
12. Frankel, L., Becker, M., Rowe, D.W. and Pearson, P.D. 2016. Meaning-making through literacy materials. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 48(3): 321-345.
13. Friesen, T.L. and Butera, G. 2013. Foundational literacy skills in children. *Early Child Development and Care*, 183(1): 24-41.
14. Gee, J.P. 2001. Reading as situated language. In: *Literacy in the New Media Age* (pp. 33-53): Routledge.
15. Johnson, K. and Jones, L. 2020. Engaging children through storytelling: the importance of voices and inflections. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48(4): 481-489.
16. Kidd, D.C. and Castano, E. 2013. Reading literary fiction improves theory of mind. *Science*, 342(6156): 377-380.
17. Marasigan, N.V. and De Las Alas M.R. 2019. Investigating parent's involvement on pupil's reading achievement. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 3(6): 132-136.
18. Mendive, S., Lissi, M.R., Bakeman, R. and Reyes, J. 2017. Maternal education and early literacy practices. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 52(1): 5-23.
19. Mol, S.E. and Bus, A.G. 2011. To read or not to read: a meta-analysis of print exposure from infancy to early adulthood. *Psychological Bulletin*, 137(2): 267-296.
20. Mol, S.E., Bus, A.G., de Jong, M.T. and Smeets, D.J.H. 2016. Added value of dialogic parent-child book readings: a meta-analysis. *Early Education and Development*, 27(4): 591-610.
21. Neumann, M.M., Hood, M. and Ford, R.M. 2013. Maternal print referencing and child literacy. *Reading Psychology*, 34(4): 367-391.
22. Sénéchal, M. and LeFevre, J. 2002. Parental involvement in the development of children's reading skill: a five-year longitudinal study. *Child Development*, 73(2): 445-460.

23. Smith, J. 2017. Parental roles in children's literacy development. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 17(2): 152-175.
24. Smith, J.K. 2018. Illustrations in children's books: purpose, types, and psychological importance. *Children and Libraries*, 16(3): 30-35.
25. Snow, C.E. and Ninio, A. 2016. The contracts of literacy: what children learn from learning to read books. *Harvard Educational Review*, 66(4): 511-542.
26. Sonnenschein, S., Baker, L., Serpell, R. and Scher, D. 2017. Early childhood parenting and child literacy: socioeconomic and ethnic differences. *Early Education and Development*, 28(1): 21-38.
27. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO]. 2008. Education for all by 2015: will we make it? EFA global monitoring report 2008. Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000156646>

Citation: Rageene Vera D. Dueñas. 2023. Parental Beliefs and Practices on Children's Emergent Literacy. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 7(8): 39-49.

Copyright: ©2023 Rageene Vera D. Dueñas. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.